

Charge and Stability of Colloids. Part XXVIII. Effect of Non-electrolyte and Temperature on the Coagulation of Chromic and Aluminium Hydroxide Sols

B. P. Yadava and Eupendra Kumar Verma

Coagulation constants, a , m , and n , of Bhattacharya's equation¹⁴ for $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ and $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ sols at various temperatures and non-electrolyte effect on $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ sol have been studied during their slow coagulation by K_2SO_4 . The increase in temperature has been found to cause a marked decrease in the value of each constant. Addition of increasing volume of sensitising non-electrolytes causes a marked decrease in the values of 'n' and 'm' and the reverse effect is observed with stabilising non-electrolyte. The value of 'n' always increases, irrespective of the nature of the non-electrolyte present during coagulation.

The results are consistent with the inferences which can be drawn from Ghosh and Gangopadhyaya's theoretical derivation¹⁷ of the above equation and also with Freundlich's assumption of the kinetic theory of coagulation¹⁶.

In investigating the relation between the electrolyte concentration and the stability of sols. Mathews and Murphy¹ and also Dumanski and Scherschnev² found the time of coagulation as a function of the electrolyte concentration. The latter authors expressed it as $t = ac^n$, where 't' is the time of coagulation and 'c' is the number of ml of electrolyte added, 'a' and 'n' being constants for a given system. The former workers¹ further pointed out that for every electrolyte, there was a limiting concentration below which coagulation was not possible.

Garner and Lewis³ and Burton and Deacon⁴ observed that on increasing the temperature, the colloidal system lost its stability. Dhar and Prakash⁵ ascribed sensitisation of a sol to the increase in the degree of hydration at higher temperatures.

According to Billitzer⁶, the sensitising effect of alcohols on negatively charged platinum sol is due to the charge reversal. Freundlich and Rona⁷ found that ferric oxide sol was sensitised by univalent precipitating ions in presence of alcohols. On adding alcohols of sufficiently high concentration, the sensitising effect changed to the stabilising effect towards NaCl. Dumanski *et al.*⁸ found this effect to become less pronounced with the increasing valency of the precipitating ion. According to Ostwald⁹ and Cassuto¹⁰, the change in dielectric constant of the medium is responsible for the sensitising influence of non-electrolytes on sols.

1. *Science*, 1921, 53, 581.
2. *J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 62, 187.
3. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 30, 1401.
4. *Kolloid Symposium Monograph*, 1928, VI, p. 77.
5. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, 34, 954.
6. *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1903, 45, 312.
7. *Biochem. Z.*, 1917, 81, 98.
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9. "Grundriss der Kolloid Chemie", 1909, p. 471.
10. "Der Kolloide Zustand der Materie", 1923, p. 152.

According to Weiser¹¹, the sensitising action of non-electrolytes is partly due to the displacement of stabilising ion or the cutting down of adsorption of a precipitating ion. Lach and Chwalinski¹² have supported the view that non-electrolytes influence the charge on the dispersed particles by reducing both the thickness of the double layer and the dielectric constant due to their adsorption. Yadava and Chatterji¹³ claim that presence of methanol accelerates the coagulation velocity of As_2S_3 sol but sugar, gelatin, and agaragar retard coagulation with $BaCl_2$.

Recently, coagulation of ferric oxide sol by several organic solvents has been found to occur due to lowering of dielectric constant to a certain critical value of the medium¹⁴. The effect of non-electrolytes of various dielectric constant has been studied in relation to the antagonism of ions¹⁵ during the slow coagulation of copper ferrocyanide sol. The effect of addition of non-electrolytes and increase of temperature of the coagulating system thus appears to be a dominating role in determining the stability on sols. An attempt has been made in this communication to study the variation of α , m , and n constants of Bhattacharya's equation¹⁴ at various temperatures and also in presence of non-electrolytes, because these constants are related directly or indirectly to the stability of sols.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental procedure adopted here for the study of temperature effect was the same as reported earlier¹⁶. The procedure adopted during the study of non-electrolyte effect is described below.

The coagulation concentration of K_2SO_4 with dialysed $Cr(OH)_3$ sol was determined at 35° in presence of non-electrolytes in 1 hour. Two more concentrations of K_2SO_4 were chosen in the range of coagulating concentrations so as to cause only slow coagulation. The progress of coagulation was followed by noting the changes produced in viscosity in each case. For each set of observations, 10 ml of sol was mixed with varying concentrations of non-electrolyte, electrolyte, and water so as to keep the total volume 20 ml each time. As the electrolytes used had no coagulating effect on the sol, the flow-time for the coagulating mixture in zero time was taken to be the same as obtained with the mixture of 10 ml sol + water + non-electrolyte, keeping total volume always 20 ml. The flow-time at zero time was noted separately in presence of each concentration of the non-electrolyte. Rest of the experimental procedure remained the same as described earlier¹⁶. The values of the constants, α , m , and n , of Bhattacharya's equation¹⁴ were determined in presence of dioxane, formamide, monomethylformamide, and methanol at 35° (Tables III-VI).

11. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 28, 1253.

12. *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1932, A159, 172.

13. *This Journal*, 1944, 21, 227.

14. Bhattacharya *et al.*, 1951, 28, 179; *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1955, 10, 551.

15. Tamotsu and Kenjiro, *Kolloid Z. Polymere*, 1962, 183, 155.

16. *This Journal*, 1962, 39, 325, 612.

The results obtained with the sols at different temperatures and stages of coagulation are recorded in Tables I and II.

TABLE I
Conc. of Cr(OH)₃ sol = 8.104 g./litre.

Temp.	Viscosity.	<i>a.</i>	<i>m.</i>	<i>n.</i> (min ⁻¹)	Temp.	Viscosity.	<i>a.</i>	<i>m.</i>	<i>n.</i> (min ⁻¹)
30°	9.50	0.00885 <i>N</i>	0.00040 <i>N</i>	0.00283	45°	7.25	0.00851 <i>N</i>	0.00025 <i>N</i>	0.00187
	10.00	0.00885	0.00040	0.00184		7.50	0.00851	0.00025	0.00085
	10.50	0.00885	0.00040	0.00123		7.75	0.00851	0.00025	0.00063
35°	8.25	0.00868	0.00033	0.00215	50	7.00	0.00846	0.00022	0.00140
	8.50	0.00868	0.00033	0.00107		7.25	0.00846	0.00022	0.00093
	8.75	0.00868	0.00033	0.00067		7.50	0.00846	0.00022	0.00062
40°	7.75	0.00856	0.00029	0.00200					
	8.00	0.00856	0.00029	0.00120					
	8.25	0.00856	0.00029	0.00066					

Stages of coagulation expressed in terms of viscosity (η) in m. poise.

TABLE II
Conc. of Al(OH)₃ sol = 8.54 g./litre.

Temp.	Viscosity.	<i>a.</i>	<i>m.</i>	<i>n.</i> (min ⁻¹)	Temp.	Viscosity.	<i>a.</i>	<i>m.</i>	<i>n.</i> (min ⁻¹)
30°	12.00	0.01035 <i>N</i>	0.00061 <i>N</i>	0.00322	40°	9.50	0.00965 <i>N</i>	0.00053 <i>N</i>	0.00194
	12.50	0.01035	0.00061	0.00219		10.00	0.00965	0.00053	0.00122
	13.00	0.01035	0.00061	0.00161		10.50	0.00965	0.00053	0.00079
35°	11.00	0.01000	0.00057	0.00252	45°	9.00	0.00928	0.00050	0.00160
	11.50	0.01000	0.00057	0.00170		9.50	0.00928	0.00050	0.00091
	12.00	0.01000	0.00057	0.00130		10.00	0.00928	0.00050	0.00048

TABLE III
Conc. of Cr(OH)₃ sol = 8.108 g./litre. Temp. = 35°.

η .	<i>a.</i>	<i>m.</i>	<i>n.</i>	η .	<i>a.</i>	<i>m.</i>	<i>n.</i>	η .	<i>a.</i>	<i>m.</i>	<i>n.</i>
A. Dioxane = 1 ml.				B. Dioxane = 2 ml.				C. Dioxane = 3 ml.			
10.00	0.00860 <i>N</i>	0.00030 <i>N</i>	0.00127	11.00	0.00830 <i>N</i>	0.00025 <i>N</i>	0.00101	11.00	0.00795 <i>N</i>	0.00020 <i>N</i>	0.00270
10.25	0.00860	0.00030	0.00073	10.25	0.00830	0.00025	0.00054	11.25	0.00795	0.00020	0.00161
10.50	0.00860	0.00030	0.00052	11.50	0.00830	0.00025	0.00030	11.50	0.00795	0.00020	0.00079

TABLE IV
Conditions same as in Table III.

η .	<i>a.</i>	<i>m.</i>	<i>n.</i>	η .	<i>a.</i>	<i>m.</i>	<i>n.</i>	η .	<i>a.</i>	<i>m.</i>	<i>n.</i>
A. Formamide = 1ml.				B. Formamide = 2ml.				C. Formamide = 3ml.			
8.50	0.00780 <i>N</i>	0.00100 <i>N</i>	0.00260	8.50	0.00740 <i>N</i>	0.00090 <i>N</i>	0.00360	8.75	0.00718 <i>N</i>	0.00083 <i>N</i>	0.00390
9.00	0.00780	0.00100	0.00100	8.75	0.00740	0.00090	0.00187	9.00	0.00718	0.00083	0.00203
9.50	0.00780	0.00100	0.00055	9.00	0.00740	0.00090	0.00101	9.25	0.00718	0.00083	0.00103

TABLE V

Conditions same as in Table III.

η .	a .	m .	n .	η .	a .	m .	n .	η .	a .	m .	n .
A. Methylformamide = 1 ml.				B. Methylformamide = 2 ml.				C. Methylformamide = 3 ml.			
9.00	0.00870N	0.00067N	0.00113	9.75	0.00900N	0.00080N	0.00491	11.00	0.00915N	0.00100N	0.00643
9.25	0.00870	0.00067	0.00065	10.00	0.00900	0.00080	0.00240	11.25	0.00915	0.00100	0.00400
9.50	0.00870	0.00067	0.00043	10.25	0.00900	0.00080	0.00144	11.50	0.00915	0.00100	0.00223

TABLE VI

Conditions same as in Table III.

η .	a .	m .	n .	η .	a .	m .	n .	η .	a .	m .	n .
A. MeOH = 1 ml.				B. MeOH = 2 ml.				C. MeOH = 3 ml.			
9.50	0.00788N	0.00044N	0.00280	9.75	0.00743N	0.00020N	0.00280	11.25	0.00720N	0.00022N	0.00313
10.00	0.00788	0.00044	0.00096	10.00	0.00743	0.00020	0.00140	11.50	0.00720	0.00022	0.00191
10.50	0.00788	0.00044	0.00043	10.25	0.00743	0.00020	0.00086	11.75	0.00720	0.00022	0.00110

N.B. In Tables III-VI η denotes viscosity expressing the stage of coagulation of the sol.

DISCUSSION

Temperature Effect

The values of constants, a , m , and n , for slow coagulation of $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ and $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ sols have been determined at different temperatures ranging between 30° and 50° . All the three constants are found to decrease with rise in temperature of the coagulating system. The value of ' a ', the critical stability concentration, which causes no coagulation even in infinite time, varies from 0.00885N to 0.00846N for $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$, when the temperature is increased from 30° to 50° . The values of ' a ' have also been found to decrease with $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ sol from 0.01035N to 0.00928N on raising the temperature from 30° to 45° . This variation indicates that the value of maximum stability concentration, i.e., ' a ', is reached at lower concentration of K_2SO_4 for each sol and less electrolyte becomes sufficient to start coagulation, showing that the stability of sols decreases as temperature increases. This is in accordance with the observations of Garner and Lewis³ and Burton and Deacon⁴.

The values of ' m ', the concentration of electrolyte above the critical value ' a ' to cause instantaneous coagulation, is also found to decrease from 0.00040N to 0.00022N for $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ sol (30 - 50°) and from 0.00061N to 0.00050N for $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ (30 - 45°). This decrease suggests that a much smaller quantity of electrolyte at higher temperatures causes instantaneous coagulation. The values of ' a ' and ' m ' are found to be independent of the stage of coagulation. The decrease observed in the value of ' m ' at higher temperatures is a further indication of the sol sensitisation. The concentration difference of the electrolyte for the slow and the rapid coagulation is reduced.

The susceptibility of the sol to the electrolyte, i.e. ' n ', is also found to decrease with the rise in temperature (Tables I and III). The justification of the results obtained is confirmed

by the arguments forwarded in our previous publication¹⁶. The nature of variation of ' n ', the susceptibility of the sol to the electrolyte, cannot be predicted due to its complex nature, depending on many factors responsible for coagulation.

Non-electrolyte Effect

The non-electrolytes, which sensitise the coagulation process of Cr (OH)₃ sol towards K₂SO₄, are found to decrease the value of ' a ', the critical stability concentration. The extent of sensitisation is greater in presence of increasing volume of non-electrolytes. The critical stability concentration in each case has been found to decrease (Tables III-VI) as all the three non-electrolytes sensitise this sol towards K₂SO₄. On adding monomethylformamide, which has a stabilising effect, the value of ' a ' increases instead of decreasing.

In presence of sensitising non-electrolytes, such as dioxane, formamide, and CH₃OH, the values of ' m ' have been found to decrease from 0.00030 to 0.00020*N*, 0.00100 to 0.00083*N*, and 0.00044 to 0.00022*N* as the volume of each non-electrolyte is increased from 1 to 3 ml. The reverse effect is observed when coagulation takes place in presence of stabilising non-electrolyte, i.e., monomethylformamide. Unlike temperature effect, the value of ' n ' is found to increase with the increasing amount of the non-electrolyte. The variation in the values of ' n ' is found to be independent of the nature of non-electrolytes added, but depends greatly on coagulation stage.

If Freundlich's assumption¹⁸ that sensitisation results from the lowering of charge on particles by adsorption on the surface of non-electrolyte of low dielectric constant is correct, the influence of non-electrolytes on coagulation constants can be explained from Ghosh and Gangopadhyaya's theoretical derivation¹⁷ of Bhattacharya's equation¹⁴. But is not possible to predict the variation of ' n ' on adding non-electrolyte to the coagulating mixture because of its complex nature.

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